

Couples HIV testing and counseling (CHTC):
A review of national policies, programs and practices in 22
high-priority countries of sub-Saharan Africa since the 2012
publication of the World Health Organization's CHTC
guidance

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ACRONYMS and ABBREVIATIONS

ANC	Antenatal clinic
ART	Antiretroviral therapy
ASSIST	Applying Science to Strengthen and Improve Systems
CFP	Couple family planning
CHTC	Couples' HIV testing and counseling
CI	Confidence interval
CSD	Counselor-supported disclosure
CTC	Care and Treatment Center
EMTCT	Elimination of mother-to-child HIV transmission
FP	Family planning
HCT	HIV counseling and testing (same as HTC)
HTC	HIV testing and counseling
IATT	Inter-Agency Task Team
LARC	Long-acting reversible contraception
P4P	Pay-for-performance
PEPFAR	The United States President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief
PITC	Provider-initiated testing and counseling
PLHIV	People living with HIV
PMTCT	Prevention of mother-to-child HIV transmission
QI	Quality improvement
RCH	Reproductive and child health
REACH-U	Realizing Expanded Access to Counseling and Testing for HIV in Uganda
RR	Risk ratio
RZHRG	Rwanda-Zambia HIV Research Group
STAR-EC	Strengthening TB and AIDS Response in East-Central Uganda
TBA	Traditional birth attendant
UNAIDS	Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS
USA	United States of America
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
VCT	Voluntary counseling and testing
WHO	World Health Organization

ABSTRACT

We conducted a narrative review of policies, programs and practices relevant to couples HIV testing and counseling (CHTC) and partner testing in the 21 Elimination of Mother-to-Child HIV Transmission (EMTCT) priority countries of sub-Saharan Africa , plus Rwanda. In the 22 countries, national HIV testing and counseling (HTC) guidance published subsequent to WHO's 2012 CHTC recommendations align with WHO guidance fairly well. It is a much more mixed scenario in regard to national HTC guidance published before 2012, as well as with other current and available country HIV guidelines. In examining new studies aiming to increase or optimize CHTC uptake and implementation we found that in no case did investigators fail to follow country recommendations. In several studies, however, investigators made innovative efforts to expand the contexts of specific policy areas. In such cases, ongoing research in a given country may be aligned more closely with WHO policy and international standards than national guidance meant to underpin research in that country. We suggest that WHO work closely with all countries in the region to harmonize national HTC and CHTC guidance with WHO recommendations, to the extent that this is feasible in the respective settings. Along with other innovative, multifaceted approaches, we also suggest that structural interventions to change social norms regarding male participation in their partners' pregnancies and antenatal care may be a promising avenue of investigation.

BACKGROUND

HIV testing and counselling (HTC) is essential for effective HIV prevention and for linking people who have HIV to antiretroviral treatment (ART) and care services. People who know they have HIV can minimize the impact of infection by maintaining ART adherence, which can further reduce the risk of transmitting the virus to sexual partners.

More than half of people living with HIV (PLHIV) are unaware that they have the infection (UNAIDS 2014). Uninfected sexual partners of PLHIV who do not know their partners have the infection are at risk of becoming infected themselves. A large proportion of stable sexual relationships ("couples") in PLHIV are HIV-serodiscordant (WHO 2012). Additionally, many people in sexual relationships are unaware of their partner's HIV status (WHO 2012). HIV-serodiscordancy in couples is a key driver of new HIV infection incidence.

Couples HIV testing and counseling (CHTC) is a long-established means of reducing HIV transmission risk in HIV-serodiscordant couples (WHO 2012). With CHTC, couples are tested for HIV together and if they choose to do so are provided a safe, supportive context for disclosing their HIV status to one another. CHTC is an approach that has the potential to improve health outcomes both for PLHIV and individuals at risk of HIV infection in sub-Saharan Africa.

CHTC can broaden the reach of HIV prevention strategies, promote earlier ART initiation, and support safer reproductive health and conception choices. CHTC can help couples to make informed decisions on many issues, including HIV prevention and reproductive health (WHO 2012). It can contribute substantively to the prevention of mother-to-child HIV transmission (PMTCT) and potentially elimination of mother-to-child transmission (EMTCT) through improved uptake of prevention services (WHO 2012). If implemented appropriately, CHTC can result in a range of other improvements in family life (e.g. better marital cohesion) as well as in society (e.g. less HIV-associated stigma) (WHO 2012).

WHO issued its Guidance on CHTC in 2012, including recommendations for antiretroviral therapy for HIV treatment and prevention in serodiscordant couples (WHO 2012). WHO recommended that couples and partners in antenatal clinic (ANC) and other settings should be offered voluntary HTC, with support for mutual disclosure. WHO also recommended that PLHIV and their sexual partners be offered voluntary HTC with support for mutual disclosure.

While many countries have adopted these recommendations in their national health policies, it is not always clear that they are being implemented in appropriate and effective ways. It can be difficult to assess their impact. Data on CHTC implementation and impact are also limited by the variety of reporting formats and a lack of specific or consistent monitoring and evaluation processes. It is necessary to understand the ways in which countries interpret and apply WHO's recommendations across programs and practices at the local level.

The Global Plan Towards the Elimination of New HIV Infections Among Children by 2015 and Keeping Their Mothers Alive was an initiative launched in 2011 by the Inter-Agency Task Team (IATT). Members of IATT include WHO, UNAIDS, other United Nations agencies, and numerous other government and non-governmental organizations. The Global Plan identified 22 EMTCT priority countries, those with the highest estimated numbers of pregnant women living with HIV. One of these EMTCT priority Countries is India. The 21 other countries are in sub-Saharan Africa and include Angola, Botswana, Burundi, Cameroon, Chad, Côte d'Ivoire, Democratic Republic of the

Congo, Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, Nigeria, South Africa, Swaziland, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia and Zimbabwe.

This report presents findings of a non-systematic, narrative review of policies, programs and practices relevant to CHTC and partner testing in the 21 EMTCT priority countries of sub-Saharan Africa, plus Rwanda. Our objectives with this report are as follows:

- Review national policies, programs and practices of 21 EMTCT Global Plan priority countries in sub-Saharan Africa, plus Rwanda, and assess the extent to which they are aligned with WHO's 2012 CHTC recommendations;
- Review and summarize promising approaches to increase CHTC in sub-Saharan Africa;
- Describe examples of successful adoption and implementation of these policies (as well as innovative approaches to CHTC in the region); and
- Identify challenges to policy adoption, program implementation and service uptake.

METHODS

Our review is multifaceted, exploring policy, practice and qualitative experience. We first set out to identify each country's current HTC guidance to ascertain its alignment with WHO's 2012 CHTC guidelines. To accomplish this, we undertook targeted online computer searches on WHO's web site and all available sites of the respective health ministries. Where ministry web sites were "down," we attempted to find archived versions online through the Internet Archive. In a serial fashion, one country at a time, we also used advanced search syntax in Google to track down relevant HTC-specific policy and guidance documents that were available on the computer servers of the IATT, the USAID/PEPFAR Resource Library, the International Association of Providers of AIDS Care (IAPAC) National HIV Policy Database and web sites of other relevant organizations. We also attempted to capture all other available and current HIV prevention or treatment guidance from the respective countries, with the aim to augment our analysis of country HTC policy where HTC-specific national documents were unavailable or they antedated WHO's 2012 CHTC guidelines.

We examined relevant sections of each document and also used the search function within electronic files to locate specific keywords. Search terms used in English-language documents included "couple", "couples," "partner," "partners," "contact tracing" and "disclosure." Search terms used in French-language documents included "couple," "partenaire," "partenaires," "conseil," "recherche des contacts" and "divulgateion." Search terms used in Portuguese-language

documents included “casais,” “parceiro,” “rastreio dos contactos,” “revelação” and “notificação.” For each country, we assessed whether its guidelines recommended HTC for couples and sexual partners in ANC settings, HTC for couples and sexual partners in other settings and HTC for sexual partners of index cases testing HIV-positive. Where documents were published in 2012 or later, we also checked to see if they referred to WHO’s CHTC guidelines.

We also conducted a narrative (non-systematic) review of the recent scientific literature to identify recent (>2010) studies reporting results of studies in which investigators assessed outcomes relevant to CHTC and partner notification (PN), particularly in ANC settings. We additionally sought to find recent articles in which barriers to CHTC and challenges to its implementation were reported, whether at the level of country policy, clinical practice or individual men and women. To find such studies we searched PubMed, Embase and Web of Science, using the following terms with the respective database’s search syntax and in appropriate combinations:

1. Angola OR Botswana OR Burundi OR Cameroon OR Chad OR Tchad OR “Côte d’Ivoire” OR “Ivory Coast” OR Congo OR Ethiopia OR Ghana OR Kenya OR Lesotho OR Malawi OR Mozambique OR Moçambique OR Namibia OR Nigeria OR Rwanda OR “South Africa” OR Swaziland OR Tanzania OR Uganda OR Zambia OR Zimbabwe
2. HIV OR HIV/AIDS OR “human immunodeficiency virus” OR “human immune deficiency virus”
3. Couple OR couples OR partner OR partners OR spouse OR spouses OR husband OR husbands OR wife OR wives OR girlfriend OR girlfriends OR boyfriend OR boyfriends OR “male involvement”
4. “testing and counseling” OR “testing and counselling” OR “counseling and testing” OR “counselling and testing” OR CHTC OR CHTC OR HTC OR HCT OR VCT OR PITC

We also searched WHO’s African Index Medicus, though our strategy was of necessity (due to database constraints) much simpler in its formulation. In all searches, search strings were designed to capture records in which terms appeared in titles, abstracts or keywords. Where we found no research for specific countries, we made targeted searches with the same strings, but with one specific country’s name (including its alternate forms) instead of all 22 countries. The search frame ranged from 1 January 2010 to the search date (19 February 2016). We additionally searched available abstracts from the International AIDS Conference (2012, 2014), International AIDS Society Conference on HIV Pathogenesis, Treatment and Prevention (2013, 2015), the Conference on

Retroviruses and Opportunistic Infection (2014, 2015) and the International Conference on AIDS and STIs in Africa (2013, 2015).

One reviewer screened all search results, selected studies for inclusion in the review and extracted data. As this is not a systematic review we did not pool data or assess evidence quality, but instead synthesize our findings in narrative and tabular form. Where feasible, we report results of comparative studies in terms of risk ratios (RR) with their 95% confidence intervals (CI).

SUMMARY of KEY FINDINGS

We briefly summarize our findings here. We provide detailed analysis in subsequent sections of this review.

National HTC guidelines

National HTC guidance published since WHO's 2012 CHTC guidelines align generally well with WHO's CHTC recommendations. Alignment is rather uneven overall in national HTC guidance published prior to WHO's 2012 recommendations. Several countries do not have specific documents addressing HTC policy or recommendations. In countries that do have such documents, we are concerned that where more comprehensive national HIV prevention guidance has subsequently been published (as discrete documents or as recommendations that should be transferred to the new document) there is the potential for national HTC guidance to have fallen by the wayside and out of use. While this may be appropriate with some older HTC guidance, obsolete or inadequate in relation to WHO's CHTC 2012 recommendations, the overall picture is unclear.

Innovative approaches

Recent research conducted in the nine countries for which we found studies is largely consistent with national HTC guidance in the respective countries. In settings where country guidance is ambiguous or seems to promote partner HTC in contexts where CHTC might be optimal, investigators have sometimes push past these limitations and, at minimum, designed an option for including CHTC. Table 1 provides a summary overview of recent research finding favorable outcomes for couples or partner HTC, whether assessed in terms of uptake or implementation. Although in many cases there is overlap, we may categorize these broadly as approaches using financial incentives, health services integration, home-based CHTC, male-friendly health services, partner invitation letters, structural interventions, capacity-building activities and innovation in CHTC methodology. In a subsequent section of this paper we will describe and analyze this research

in greater depth. These CHTC programs and approaches to implementation and expansion may hold promise for replication in other settings in sub-Saharan Africa.

Table 1. Innovative approaches: Recent studies reporting HTC outcomes

Number of studies	Approach	Countries	Key finding
4	Health services integration	Cameroon, Malawi, Uganda, Zambia	Increased male partner HTC; one describes CHTC with adolescent partner
4	Home-based CHTC	Kenya, Mozambique	Increased male partner HTC
4	Partner invitation letters	Malawi, Tanzania	Increased CHTC
3	Capacity building	Botswana, Côte d'Ivoire, Kenya, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda, Swaziland	Describes capacity-building efforts; describes CHTC implementation
2	Structural intervention	Zambia	Increased CHTC
1	Financial incentives for providers	Rwanda	Increased CHTC
1	Male engagement	Mozambique	Increased male partner HTC
1	Methodology	Kenya	Increased CHTC

Program reports from internationally funded efforts

In examining quarterly and annual progress reports developed by HTC program implementers in response to funder requirements, we identified several brief accounts of creative strategies used in Burundi, Mozambique, Tanzania and Uganda to engage and recruit couples for CHTC. According to program documents, male partner recruitment in Burundi and Tanzania study settings has increased significantly through the use of a multifaceted community-based intervention. We present these data later in the paper.

Challenges to CHTC implementation and uptake

We identified several challenges to appropriate CHTC and partner HTC implementation and barriers to its use. These occurred on three main levels, those of a) national policy, b) health systems and c) couples and individuals. On the national policy level, we report findings of our analysis of country HTC guidance. On the level of health systems, we describe the findings of five qualitative research studies conducted in Nigeria, Rwanda, Uganda, and Zambia. For couples and individuals, we report barriers to HTC uptake identified in a systematic review of 24 African studies, as well as barriers

noted in two additional studies published subsequent to the systematic review. We present our findings in a later section of this review.

RESULTS in DETAIL

Alignment of country HTC policy with WHO 2012 guidance

We reviewed the most recent national HIV guidelines and policy statements for the 21 Global Plan countries, plus Rwanda. We first describe our findings regarding countries with published documents relevant to HTC, specifically regarding their alignment with WHO's 2012 CHTC guideline. We then report alignments to this guidance of any CHTC or partner-HTC recommendations found in each country's other current HIV guidelines (e.g. PMTCT guidelines, ART guidelines). All country guidance and policy documents may be found here: <https://goo.gl/GrNxmS>

1. Countries with HTC-specific guidance

Seventeen (77%) of 22 countries have published guidance documents specifically concerned with HTC. Countries with HTC-specific guidance documents include Botswana, Chad, Côte d'Ivoire, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Kenya, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, Nigeria, South Africa, Swaziland, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe.

- Publication dates range from 2002 (Côte d'Ivoire) to 2015 (Kenya, Malawi, Mozambique).
- Countries with no identified HTC-specific guidance included Angola, Burundi, Cameroon, Lesotho and Rwanda.
- Despite extensive internet searches, HTC guidance documents from Malawi and Mozambique were available only as very late and advanced but non-finalized versions. It is unclear whether this HTC guidance from either country has formally been released. For the purpose of the current analysis we will consider each country's HTC guidance to have been released.
- For Malawi, we also identified an HTC training manual from 2013.
- The guidance document from Chad was not a guideline documents *per se*, but was a manual for training health workers in conducting HTC.
- Given the paucity of available data, for the purpose of the current analysis we will consider these documents to represent HTC guidance for the respective countries.

2. HTC-specific, published after WHO's 2012 CHTC guidelines

Of 17 countries with HTC-specific guidelines, only five (31%) have updated their national HTC guidelines since WHO's guidance on CHTC was published in 2012.

- These countries were Kenya (2015), Malawi (2015), Mozambique (2015), Tanzania (2013) and Zimbabwe (2014).
- Zambia (2014) released a national HTC implementation plan.
- Alignment with WHO's 2012 CHTC guideline was generally good across the five countries, though in several cases the necessity of CHTC (as couples) in ANC settings was not quite explicit.
- Mozambique and Tanzania recommend testing of pregnant women and their partners in these settings, but this is not necessarily the same as CHTC.
- The Malawi draft guidance and Zimbabwe appropriately refer to testing couples in ANC settings. The Malawi training manual (2013) refers only to partner testing in ANC settings.
- Kenya does not specify ANC settings, but suggests that women seeking "maternal and child health services" should be encouraged by providers to bring male partners to the clinic for CHTC.
- With regard to CHTC in other settings, all countries refer appropriately to couples testing and provide appropriate recommendations in regard to HTC for PLHIV and their sexual partners with support for mutual disclosure of HIV status.
- Only Zimbabwe referred to WHO's 2012 CHTC guideline. Tanzania referred to WHO's 2007 guideline on provider-initiated testing and counseling (PITC). Kenya and Malawi referred to WHO's 2012 guideline on service delivery approaches for HTC. Mozambique referred to WHO's 2015 guideline on HTS.

Please see Table 2 (next page).

Table 2. Countries with HTC-specific guidelines published 2013 or later: Alignment with WHO 2012 CHTC guidance

Country	Year of most recent policy document	Refers to WHO 2012 CHTC guidance?	Offer HTC to couples & partners in ANC?	Offer HTC to couples & partners in other settings?	Offer HTC to PLHIV & partners?
Kenya	2015	No [‡]	Yes*	Yes	Yes
Malawi draft	2015	No [‡]	Yes	Yes	Yes
Malawi training	2013	No [§]	Partners [†]	Yes	Yes
Mozambique draft	2015	No	Partners [†]	Yes	Yes
Tanzania	2013	No [°]	Partners [†]	Yes	Yes
Zambia**	2014	No ^{††}	Yes	Yes	Yes
Zimbabwe	2014	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

*Maternal and child health settings, not explicitly ANC settings.

†Recommends that sexual partners of pregnant women testing HIV-positive should receive HTC, but does not recommend CHTC *per se* in ANC settings.

‡Refers to WHO 2012, HTC service delivery approaches.

§Refers to WHO 2005, HIV rapid testing and WHO 2010, Delivering test results

||Refers to WHO 2015, Consolidated guidelines on HTS.

°Refers to WHO 2007, PITC guidance

**Strategic planning document only.

††Acknowledges WHO support.

3. HTC-specific, published before WHO's 2012 CHTC guidelines

In 12 countries with HTC-specific policy documents published before WHO's 2012 couples guidance, alignment with current WHO CHTC policy was rather varied.

- Only Namibia explicitly recommends CHTC in ANC settings.
- In ANC settings, Botswana and Uganda recommend that sexual partners of pregnant women receive HTC, but this is not necessarily the same as CHTC.
- Eleven of 12 countries recommend providers offer HTC to couples and sexual partners in other settings; Democratic Republic of Congo does not raise this possibility. Only Botswana, Chad, Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, Namibia and Zambia describe the need to offer HTC to PLHIV and their sexual partners.
- In most countries, recommendations to provide support to couples or partners for mutual disclosure were made explicit. No mention of such support was found in documents for Democratic Republic of Congo, South Africa or Swaziland. Ghana's guidance suggests that persons receiving individual HTC could receive his or her test results in "couples counselling"

with sexual partners. It is not clear that the other partner would also have had HTC prior to this meeting.

- Botswana’s guidance was ambiguous, suggesting that service providers could provide ongoing counseling to patients testing HIV-positive so that they may overcome barriers to informing sexual partners.
- Guidance for both Nigeria and Swaziland may reflect a misunderstanding of the phrase “support for mutual disclosure,” as HTC guidance for both countries describes “[t]he need for disclosure and mutual support...”, apparently suggesting that partners should support each other in HIV status disclosure.
- Guidance from Côte d’Ivoire suggests only that persons receiving HTC should be encouraged to notify sexual partners of test results.

Please see Table 3.

Table 3. Countries with HTC-specific guidelines published before 2013: Alignment with WHO 2012 CHTC guidance

Country	Year of most recent policy document	Refers to any WHO HTC guidance?	Offer HTC to couples & partners in ANC?	Offer HTC to couples & partners in other settings?	Offer HTC to PLHIV & partners?
Botswana	2009	Yes	Partners*	Yes	Yes
Chad†	2011	No	No	Yes	Yes
Côte d’Ivoire	2002	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
DR Congo	2004	No	Partners*	No	No
Ethiopia	2007	No	No	Yes	No
Ghana	2008	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Namibia	2011	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Nigeria	2011	No	No	Yes	No
South Africa	2010	Yes	No	Yes	No
Swaziland	2006	Yes	No	Yes	No
Uganda	2010	Yes	Partners*	Yes	No
Zambia	2006	Yes	No	Yes	Yes

*Recommends that sexual partners of pregnant women testing HIV-positive should receive HTC, but does not recommend CHTC *per se* in ANC settings.

†Training manual only.

4. All countries: HIV guidelines not specifically focused on HTC

Whether or not they had recent HTC-specific policy documents, we thought it possible that countries would also provide HTC recommendations within other current HIV guidance. We found current guidance on HIV prevention, care, integrated prevention and care and PMTCT for all countries except Chad. Within each document we attempted to identify guidance relevant to CHTC or HTC for partners.

- Nine countries (Burundi, Cameroon, Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Lesotho, Rwanda, Swaziland, Tanzania and Zambia) included recommendations that providers should offer HTC to partners or couples in ANC settings.
- Eight countries (Burundi, Cameroon, Ethiopia, Lesotho, Malawi, Rwanda, Swaziland and Zambia) included recommendations that providers should offer HTC to partners or couples in other settings.
- Thirteen countries (Angola, Cameroon, Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Mozambique, Nigeria, Rwanda, Swaziland, Tanzania and Zambia) recommended that providers offer HTC to PLHIV and their partners.

Please see Table 4.

Table 4: All countries: HTC and CHTC in other current & available care, PMTCT or integrated prevention and treatment guidelines (not including HTC-specific documents)

Country	Year of most recent policy document	Scope of document	Offer HTC to couples & partners in ANC?	Offer HTC to couples & partners in other settings?	Offer HTC to PLHIV & partners?
Angola	2014	Care	No	No	Yes
Botswana	2012	Integrated	No	No	No
Burundi	2014	Care	Yes	Yes	No
Cameroon	2014	Integrated	Yes	Yes	Yes
Cameroon	2006	PMTCT	Partners [†]	No	Yes
Chad*	2011	Planning	Partners [†]	No	Yes
Côte d'Ivoire	2012	PMTCT	No	No	No
Côte d'Ivoire	2013	Care	No	No	No
DR Congo	2013	Care	No	No	No
Ethiopia	2014	Integrated	Yes	Yes	Yes
Ghana	2014	PMTCT	Yes	No	Yes
Kenya‡	2012	PMTCT	No	No	No

Kenya	2014	Integrated	Yes	No	Yes
Lesotho	2014	Integrated	Yes	Yes	Yes
Malawi‡	2014	Integrated	No	Yes	Yes
Mozambique	2014	Integrated	No	No	Yes
Namibia	2014	Care	No	No	No
Nigeria	2010	Care	No	No	Yes
Nigeria*	2014	Planning	No	No	No
Rwanda	2013	Integrated	Yes	Yes	Yes
South Africa	2015	Integrated	No	No	No
Swaziland	2015	Integrated	Yes	Yes	Yes
Tanzania‡	2013	PMTCT	Yes	No	Yes
Uganda	2012	Integrated	No	No	No
Zambia	2010	PMTCT	Yes	Yes	Yes
Zambia	2013	Integrated	Partners†	No	Yes
Zimbabwe‡	2014	Integrated	No	No	No

*National strategic plan only

† Recommends that sexual partners of pregnant women testing HIV-positive should receive HTC, but does not recommend CHTC *per se*.

‡ Also has post-2012 HTC-specific guidance document.

Alignment of programs and practices with respective country policies

We reviewed the scientific literature to ascertain how well CHTC programs and activities in the 21 Global Plan countries and Rwanda align with HTC guidance from the respective countries. Searches of bibliographic databases and recent conference abstracts yielded 193 unique records. From these, we identified 20 (10.4%) studies conducted in 2012 or later that reported relevant program outcomes in any of the 22 countries.

Only nine (41%) countries (Cameroon, Kenya, Malawi, Mozambique, Rwanda, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda and Zambia) are represented in this literature. Other “grey literature” program reports describe research in Burundi, Mozambique, Tanzania and Uganda.

We also identified one systematic review and seven additional studies reporting qualitative and other data relevant to barriers to and facilitators of CHTC, implementation issues and related concerns in any of the 22 countries.

Researchers report results from several innovative types of programs. These include financial incentives for providers to offer CHTC (Rwanda); health services integration for improving CHTC uptake (Cameroon, Kenya, Uganda, Zambia); partner invitation letters (Malawi, Tanzania); home-

based CHTC (Kenya, Mozambique); and development of male-friendly health services for improving CHTC uptake (Malawi, Mozambique, Tanzania). We also report the results of a structural intervention (Zambia), of a methodologic innovation to CHTC itself (Kenya) and of South-to-South CHTC capacity-building efforts (many countries).

In the next section we summarize this research and within each research setting, contextualize it in terms of CHTC policy in the respective countries.

Additionally, we provide brief descriptive data for several CHTC recruitment strategies, taken from annual, semi-annual or quarterly reports to United States government funding sources. Although reports from Burundi suggest that a multifaceted community-based approach has greatly increased male partner testing in that country, most descriptions do not include results. It may be unclear whether the strategies described are even effective. Even so, they may still serve to illustrate local approaches that have not yet reached the peer-reviewed literature or scientific conferences.

Following this section, we will provide analysis of challenges to policy adoption, program implementation and service uptake. Electronic files for each included study may be downloaded here: <https://goo.gl/GrNxmS>

Innovative approaches to increasing CHTC implementation and uptake in 21 Global Plan countries and Rwanda

We report the findings of studies using several innovative approaches to increase CHTC implementation and uptake in nine of the 22 countries. The interventional studies resulted in improvements in CHTC uptake and male partner testing. Please see Table 5, and the analysis below.

Table 5. Summary characteristics of included studies.

Study	Approach	Country	Key finding
Ahmed 2015	Capacity building	Many countries	Reports high-level national commitments to scaling up CHTC
Appiagyei 2012	Structural intervention	Zambia	Clinic changed social norms re: male ANC attendance
Audet 2016	Male-friendly services	Mozambique	Of male partners reached (67%), 34% received HTC (vs. baseline 9%)
Bandomia 2013	Home-based HTC	Mozambique	Male partner CHTC acceptance increased 41% (from 58% to 82%).
Becker 2014	FP with CHTC	Malawi	Of couples accepting any service (89%), 97% accepted CHTC
Brunie 2016	FP with HTC	Uganda	Male HTC uptake 80% (vs. 50% in females)

De Walque 2015	Financial incentives for providers	Rwanda	CHTC in Rwanda increased 18%
Inambao 2014	Structural intervention	Zambia	Monthly daily average of couples receiving CHTC changed from 3.7 to 7.0
Jefferys 2015	“Official” invitation letters	Tanzania	Of couples attending ANCs (53.5%), 81% received CHTC
Kababu 2015	Methodology	Kenya	CHTC uptake 46% with standardized disclosure protocol, vs. 12% with usual protocol
Kilembe 2015	Capacity building	South Africa	Pilot CHTC implementation, 28 personnel trained, 907 couples received CHTC
Krakowiak 2016	Home-based HTC	Kenya	CHTC 77% in home-based HTC arm vs. 24% in partner invitation arm
Lockard 2015	LARC with CHTC	Zambia	16% of couples had adolescent female partner; 31% of these already pregnant
Mark 2015	Home-based HTC w/syphilis testing	Kenya	Of men who accepted syphilis testing (92%), 91% accepted CHTC
Muffih 2015	PN with Option B+	Cameroon	Of male partners contacted (83%), 61% received HTC
Nyondo 2015	Invitation cards	Malawi	CHTC 28% in couples with cards, vs. 19% without
Osoti 2014	Home-based HTC	Kenya	CHTC uptake much higher in home-based HTC vs. clinic-based (RR 2.42, 95% CI 1.94 to 3.01)
Rosenberg 2015	Invitation plus partner tracing	Malawi	CHTC 74% in couples with invitation plus tracing, vs. 52% with invitation only
Theuring 2016	“Official” invitation letters	Tanzania	CHTC 30% with “official” invitation vs. 28% with verbal invitation
Tichacek 2014	Capacity building	Zambia	In three years, provided 314 trainings, opened 53 CHTC clinics, provided CHTC to >68,000 couples in region with no previous CHTC services

FP: family planning. LARC: Long-acting reversible contraception

1. Financial incentives for providers

We found one study in which healthcare providers were compensated financially for increasing CHTC rates in married couples.

De Walque and colleagues (2015) report the effect of Rwanda’s national pay-for-performance (P4P) scheme on HTC rates, as measured through a prospective impact evaluation they nested within the country’s P4P scale-up between 2006-2008. This scale-up was concurrent with that of the country’s HIV treatment services. Providers received incentive payments amounting to USD \$0.92 per individual tested and USD \$4.59 per new couple tested.

- Compared to baseline probabilities for couples in 2006, P4P increased the probability that both members of a serodiscordant couple had received HTC by 14.7% ($p=0.03$). This represented an 18.1% increase from baseline rates.
- The impact on HTC uptake probability was not significant on couples overall (8.6%; $p=0.19$) or in couples with non-discordant HIV status (7.2%; $p=0.30$).
- Investigators suggest that the impact of P4P on CHTC could be more pronounced in more static HIV service-provision settings. Investigators report no data on linkages to care or adverse outcomes.

Rwanda does not have a guidance document specific to HTC, but CHTC recommendations in the country's HIV prevention and care guidelines (Rwanda 2013) are consistent with those in WHO's 2012 couples guidance. Data collected for this study are rather old by now, and P4P is not discussed in Rwanda's CHTC guidance. Rwanda's CHTC rates were not assessed in the most recent (2014-2015) Demographic and Health Survey (USAID 2016), but men's 12-month HTC rate increased from 11% in 2005 to 37.7% in 2010 (USAID 2016). It is 36.7% in the current report (USAID 2016).

2. Health services integration

Four studies in Cameroon, Malawi, Uganda and Zambia explored the ways that CHTC uptake or partner notification services could be improved through health service integration.

Muffih and colleagues (2015) in Cameroon describe their experience implementing partner notification services within the country's Option B+ program. In Option B+, pregnant women testing HIV-positive began lifelong ART immediately, regardless of CD4 cell count. From March 2013 to September 2014, 823 pregnant women tested HIV-positive at 22 Option B+ sites. They identified 840 male partners. The program's trained "Health Advisors" contacted 693 (82.5%) of these men and either facilitated HIV status disclosure by the female partners or confidentially informed male partners of their HIV exposure.

- In clinics, homes or other settings, 421 (60.8%) male partners received HTC, with 139 (33.0%) testing HIV-positive.
- Nearly all ($n=138$; 99.3%) of these male partners were linked to care.
- Investigators report no adverse events.
- While investigators do not report baseline rates for partner testing, these rates are generally consistent with the program's experience with all partner notification in 2009-2010. In an

earlier report (Henley 2013), investigators describe contacting 83.8% of index patient sexual partners, of whom 66.8% received HTC. A larger proportion (50.1%) of these partners tested HIV-positive in the earlier study.

Becker and colleagues (2014) in Blantyre, Malawi tested an integration of couple family planning (CFP) services with CHTC. A pair of counselors (one male and one female) visited couples enrolled in the study. With each couple, counselors conducted baseline interviews on reproductive health topics and assessed couple attitudes about pregnancy, communication and emotional closeness. Separately from male partners, counselors asked women if they agreed to CFP with CHTC, CFP only or CHTC only. Male partners were offered the respective service or services accepted by the women.

- Counselors reached 167 (92.7%) of 180 enrolled couples.
- Of 149 (89.2%) couples accepting any service, 145 (97.3%) couples received CHTC.
- Investigators do not discuss linkage to care outcomes, but do note that no violent incidents were reported in couples tested.

In Uganda, Brunie and colleagues (2016) implemented a community-based service model that integrated provision of family planning (FP) services and HTC. Eight health centers in with existing FP services in two purposively selected districts were randomized to provide integrated services or FP services only. In addition to data from programmatic records, a sample of participants and all VHT members were surveyed 10 months after the intervention.

- Thirty-six village health teams (VHT) offered HTC to 646 participants, of whom 577 (89.2%) accepted it. Although more women tested than men, a larger proportion of men offered HTC accepted it (80% vs. 49.6%). More than one-third (35.9%) of participants receiving HTC were testing for the first time.
- In 108 women who received HTC and had male partners at the time, 92 (85.2%) recalled that VHTs offered CHTC. Only 23 (21.3%), however, received CHTC.
- More than two-thirds (68.5%) of women with partners who tested alone reported sharing results with their partners. Of three participants testing HIV-positive with the VHT, all were linked to care. Investigators reported no adverse events.

Lockard and colleagues (2015) in the Zambia-Emory HIV Research Project (ZEHRP), a sub-project of the long-running Rwanda-Zambia HIV Research Group (RZHRG), also integrated FP services with

CHTC. They describe the proportion of adolescent women (age <20 years) attending clinics with male partners. In March 2013, this program began to offer Long-Acting Reversible Contraception (LARC) with CHTC in 53 government clinics in six cities.

- Of 83,339 couples tested, 13,525 (16.2%) had an adolescent woman and 1,836 (2.2%) had an adolescent male partner.
- Nearly one-third (31.3%) of adolescent women were already pregnant.
- In 92.4% of couples with adolescent women, both partners tested HIV-negative; in 4.0%, both tested HIV-positive. In 2.1% of such couples, the woman tested HIV-positive and the man HIV-negative. Men tested HIV-positive and women HIV-negative in 1.5% of couples.
- Investigators do not describe linkage to care or any adverse events.

HIV health service delivery outcomes can often be improved when integrated with other HIV services (Medley 2015) or with services in other areas of health care (Suthar 2013, Suthar 2014). Cameroon's CHTC and partner services recommendations are provided only in the country's integrated HIV prevention and care guidelines (Cameroon 2014), but these align well with WHO's 2012 couples guidance. The partner services activities described by Muffih and colleagues are consistent with those recommended in Cameroon's guidelines.

In offering CFP with CHTC in home settings, the research by Becker (2014) in Malawi goes somewhat beyond the recommendations of that country's HTC guidance, although it must be said that this guidance was developed after publication of Becker's study. Malawi encourages home-based testing as one of several community-based approaches that could be used. While it mentions several different populations that could be targeted for these community-based approaches (e.g. women aged 15-24, fisher-folk, sex workers and others), Malawi makes no mention of couples in this context. Malawi's guideline does suggest that CHTC should be encouraged for couples who wish to make informed decisions about family planning methods.

Uganda's HTC guidance (Uganda 2010) is rather old and while in most respects it aligns with WHO's 2012 couples guidelines, it does not explicitly recommend that sexual partners of PLHIV should receive HTC. The country's current "integrated" HIV guidelines (Uganda 2012) do not adequately address CHTC or HTC, suggesting only – without mention of HIV testing – that FP services be offered for preventing HIV transmission to sexual partners: "Quality FP counseling and services should reinforce clients' ability to limit HIV transmission to HIV-negative partners and to infants." The FP

integration study in Uganda by Brunie (2016) thus follows Uganda's current FP-oriented HIV prevention guidance but pushes somewhat beyond it through also offering CHTC.

Zambia's 2006 HTC guidelines and its 2014 HTC planning document suggest that where possible, HTC should be integrated in FP activities. However, neither document explicitly mentions CHTC in FP contexts. Zambia's 2010 PMTCT and 2013 integrated HIV guidelines consider FP only in the context of persons in whom HIV has already been diagnosed.

3. Invitation letters

Partner invitation letters have been used widely in sub-Saharan Africa to increase male partner HTC. Four recent studies in Malawi and Tanzania explored the use of invitation letters to male partners of pregnant women. Women attending ANCs delivered written or verbal invitations to male partners with the goal of their accompanying women for CHTC.

Nyondo and colleagues (2015) in Blantyre, Malawi tested an intervention of CHTC invitation cards for male partners of pregnant women. Investigators randomized 462 pregnant women attending ANCs without male partners to the intervention group or usual care.

- Between June and December 2013, intervention group women (n=230) received cards to give to their male partners, inviting them to attend CHTC.
- At study's end, 65/230 (28.26%) of intervention group women attended CHTC with their male partners, compared to 44/232 (18.97%) of those not receiving cards (RR 1.49, 95% CI 1.06 to 2.09).
- Investigators report that the proportion of ART uptake by women testing HIV-positive was lower than the 93% Malawi average during the study period, but they do not quantify that proportion.
- Investigators do not report any adverse events.

Rosenberg and colleagues (2015) in Lilongwe, Malawi conducted an RCT in 200 pregnant women who had recently tested HIV-positive but had not yet had CHTC. Between March and October 2014, women were provided CHTC invitation letters to give to their male partners and were randomized to either "invitation-only" (n=100) or "invitation plus tracing" (n=100). Clinic staff attempted to trace male partners in the "invitation plus tracing" group by telephone, in the community or by home visits if they did not present for CHTC. Baseline CHTC rates were not reported.

- At study's end, 74 "invitation plus tracing" couples and 52 "invitation only" couples presented to the clinic and had CHTC (RR 1.42, 95% CI 1.14 to 1.78). (Investigators reported these findings in terms of risk difference (RD): 22%, 95% CI 8.9% to 35.1%; p=0.001.)
- In 181 women for whom investigators had follow-up data, there were very few adverse events, with two reporting marriage dissolution and one reporting emotional distress. No woman reported intimate partner violence.

In Mbeya District, Tanzania, Jefferys and colleagues (2015) provided pregnant women attending ANCs for the first time in their current pregnancies, unaccompanied by male partners, with "official invitation letters" requesting male partner attendance at next ANC visits. Letters explained that important information about pregnancy and parenthood would be provided and did not mention anything about HIV testing. Letters were "courteous and formal" and were signed by regional medical officers. Investigators recruited 318 women to the study between March and June 2013.

- In 237 (72.9%) women who subsequently returned to ANCs, 232 (97.9%) reported giving invitation letters to male partners.
- Overall, 170 (53.5%) women and their partners attended the ANC together during the study period. Of these, 81% received CHTC.
- Twenty-one percent of male partners attended ANC with women only after receiving a second invitation letter.
- The proportion of couples attending ANC together varied significantly among several study sites (from 31% in an urban clinic to 76% in a rural clinic) and was dependent on several covariates.
- Investigators report baseline estimates of 2% to 19% CHTC attendance, depending on study site.

In a related quasi-RCT during a four-week period between April and May 2013, Theuring and colleagues (2016) in Mbeya District, Tanzania assigned pregnant women (n=199) to present male partners with the "official invitation letters" described above or to invite male partners verbally to attend CHTC.

- All but three of 59 (60.8%) intervention group women returning for ANC visits reported giving invitation letters to male partners. All but three of 65 (63.7%) "verbal invitation" women returning for ANC visits reported inviting male partners as instructed.

- Thirty (30.3%) of 97 intervention group women and 28/102 (27.5%) of “verbal invitation” women returned with male partners for CHTC (RR 1.13, 95% CI 0.73 to 1.74). Investigators report these findings in terms of odds ratio (OR): OR 1.2; 95% CI 0.6 to 2.2.
- There was no statistical significance in the difference between groups, but investigators point out that only 1.7% of male partners had received CHTC in the three months preceding the study period.

While Malawi’s HTC guidelines specify that CHTC should be offered to pregnant women and male partners in ANC settings, they do not describe a need for male engagement or making special efforts to bring men in to ANCs for CHTC. Tanzania’s HTC guidance, on the other hand, clearly state that innovative approaches are needed to increase HTC in males, particularly with their partners. While Tanzania’s guidance is clear that male partner testing should be encouraged in ANC and other settings, it stops short of recommending CHTC in ANC settings. Given the totality of Tanzania’s recommendations in this regard, it seems likely that this omission was not intentional, but a point that is slightly unclear.

The evidence from the studies of partner invitation letters suggest that while response rates may be relatively low, they could still be much higher than response rates without invitations. In settings with minimal CHTC uptake, inviting male partners to CHTC could potentially be an inexpensive and easily implemented approach to improving it, if only to a small degree. Earlier research in Kenya (Farquhar 2004), South Africa (Mohlala 2011), Tanzania, (Msuya 2008, Becker 2010) and Uganda (Byagumisha 2011) also found improved CHTC uptake when male partners were invited through written or verbal invitations to attend, though attendance was often still suboptimal.

4. Home-based HTC

Four studies described recent research in which investigators in Kenya and Mozambique sought to improve uptake of CHTC or male partner testing through reaching women and male partners in their homes.

In Nyanza province, Kenya, Osoti and colleagues (2014) assessed CHTC uptake when male partners were tested at home, compared to testing male partners at ANC appointments. From July 2012 to July 2013, 300 pregnant women attending ANCs were randomized to clinic-based or home-based CHTC.

- In male partners of women assigned to home-based CHTC, more than twice as many were reached (RR 2.37, 95% CI 1.90 to 2.96) and tested (RR 2.42, 95% CI 1.94 to 3.01) with home-based CHTC, compared to male partners of women assigned to clinic-based CHTC.

Mark and colleagues (2015) in Kisumu, Kenya explored the impact of offering rapid syphilis testing in addition to home-based CHTC and education during pregnancies. Investigators report data gathered from April to July 2014 in 73 couples.

- Syphilis prevalence is low in Kenya, but compared to men who refused it, men who accepted syphilis testing were more likely to accept CHTC (OR 10.2, 95% CI 1.05 to 89.3; $p=0.02$).
- Sixty-seven (91.7%) men accepted syphilis testing, of whom 61 (91.0%) also accepted CHTC.
- Including three men who refused syphilis testing but accepted CHTC, nine (14.5%) men tested HIV-positive.
- Investigators do not report on linkages to care or adverse events.

In Mozambique's Nampula Province, Bandomia and colleagues (2013) implemented a program of home-based CHTC. From January 2012 through March 2013, healthcare facilities providing ANC-based CHTC offered referrals to "community-based HIV tester-counselors," who visited HIV-positive pregnant women in their homes.

- Community-based tester-counselors visited homes of 797 pregnant women living with HIV.
- The proportion of male partners accepting CHTC with female partners changed from 58% in January-March 2012 to 82% in January-March 2013, an increase of 41.3%.
- Investigators do not report adverse events or rates of linkage to care.

In Kisumu, Kenya, Krakowiak and colleagues (2016) conducted an RCT in 2013-2014 in which a home-based CHTC intervention was compared against a control condition of letters inviting male partners to clinic-based CHTC. At their first ANC visits, pregnant women were randomized to intervention ($n=306$) or control ($n=295$) conditions.

- At six months, pregnant women and male partners in the home-based HTC arm were much more likely to have received CHTC (RR 3.17, 95% CI 2.53 to 3.98).
- Considering only male partners, they were more than twice as likely to have received HTC (RR 2.10, 95% CI 1.81 to 2.42).

- Women were more than twice as likely to know their male partner’s HIV serostatus (RR 2.27, 95% CI 1.93 to 2.67).
- A larger proportion of serodiscordant couples was discovered in the home-based HTC arm than in the invitation letters arm (RR 3.38, 95% CI 1.70 to 6.71).
- Investigators do not report on adverse events or linkage to care.

Home-based HTC has been used extensively in sub-Saharan Africa (Sabapathy 2013). In addition to reaching people who may not otherwise be reached for testing, home-based HTC can help to diminish community stigma, facilitate early diagnosis for those testing positive and potentially reach more couples than with other approaches (WHO 2012 HTC Implementation). A 2012 systematic review of home-based HTC found no studies specifically focused on home-based CHTC (Sabapathy 2012). Similarly, a 2013 systematic review on community-based HTC approaches found no such studies, but reviewers note that implementation of home-based and other community approaches to HTC helps to increase proportions of couples receiving it (Suthar 2013).

Both Kenya and Mozambique issued new HTC-specific guidance in 2015 (Kenya 2015, Mozambique 2015), and while Kenya’s guidance encourages the use of home-based HTC for reaching sexual partners, it does not address CHTC in this context. Mozambique’s HTC guidelines provide strong support for community-based approaches to making HTC accessible to partners, families, key populations and others, and while they do not mention CHTC in this context, they do suggest that door-to-door home visits for HTC should be encouraged.

5. Male-friendly health services

We found one study that that sought to make male partners feel more comfortable about attending ANC with pregnant women. A “Male Champion” intervention in Mozambique used community-based accompaniment and support as well as other measures to improve HTC rates in male partners.

From June 2012 through March 2014, Audet and colleagues (2016) in rural Inhassunge district, Zambézia, Mozambique, implemented a community-based intervention designed to increase male partner participation in antenatal care services. “Male Champions,” selected by community leaders and given training in maternal and child health issues as well as gender dynamics, counseled men and facilitated their engagement. Traditional birth attendants (TBAs) were integrated in the health

system, and among other duties engaged with pregnant women about the importance of antenatal care.

Notified by TBAs of a woman's pregnancy, male champions would seek to visit male partners as early in the pregnancy as possible. In home, community and clinic settings, male champions engaged male partners in dialogue and generally attempted to de-stigmatize men's engagement in ANC services, and often accompanied couples to ANCs. When couples arrived at ANCs, specially-trained counselors ascertained each partner's interest in CHTC with mutual disclosure. If either partner refused, each partner was offered HTC, without disclosure. They otherwise received CHTC. If couples receiving CHTC both agreed, they could disclose each partner's serostatus to the male champion. If only the woman received HTC, she also had the option to disclose her serostatus to the male champion or to the TBA. This knowledge enabled male champions and TBAs to provide support for ART uptake or other support during and after the pregnancy. The project also created a "male-friendly" clinical environment with private rooms for CHTC and key discussions, and other components.

- TBAs reached 4024 (92%) of 4355 pregnant women and male champions reached 2928 (67%) male partners.
- Compared to before the intervention, the study found improvement in terms of male partner accompaniment to ANCs (first ANC visit: 5% vs. 34%, $p < 0.001$; any ANC visit: 10% vs. 37%; $p < 0.001$).
- Investigators do not actually describe uptake of CHTC *per se*, but report it in terms of ANC-based HTC in the respective partners. HTC increased in women from 81% to 92% ($p < 0.001$). In all male partners, including those not reached by male champions, HTC increased from 9% to 34% ($p < 0.001$).
- The intervention was associated with an increase in lifelong ART (Option B+) uptake in women testing HIV-positive (adjusted odds ratio [aOR] 2.68, 95% CI 1.59 to 4.51) but not with PrEP uptake in HIV-negative female partners of HIV-positive men (aOR 1.09, 95% CI 0.79 to 1.50).
- Investigators report some adverse events: several male champions and TBAs were accused by community members of being sorcerers, and were assaulted.

Mozambique's 2015 HTC guidelines are clear about the need to offer HTC to male partners of women attending ANCs, but are not explicit that it should be delivered as CHTC. Audet's study

aimed to increase HTC in male partners and while it placed an emphasis on CHTC, any HTC in male partners was a desirable outcome. Again, Mozambique's guidelines support community-based approaches, though they do not explicitly suggest the need to increase HTC in men by encouraging them to participate in women's antenatal care.

6. Structural intervention

Two studies in Zambia reports on a structural intervention. Structural interventions are those that seek to change contextual or environmental factors, especially accessibility, availability or acceptability, rather than focusing only on changing patient behavior (Blankenship 2006).

Inambao and colleagues (2014) with the RZHRG in Ndola, Zambia examined logbooks from ANCs and from HTC services in government clinics for the period 2011-2013 to assess changes in CHTC rates. Zambia's government had instructed government clinics to scale up provision of CHTC and male partner HTC. The government emphasized integrated service provision on weekdays, in addition to the usual stand-alone clinics and weekend-only service availability.

- Over a three year period, the monthly average number of couples receiving CHTC per weekday in government HTC clinics nearly doubled, increasing from 3.7 to 7.0 couples per day.
- In ANCs, the monthly average number of couples receiving CHTC daily increased from 13.1 to 16.5.

Appiagyei and colleagues (2012) with the RZHRG also describe the impact of Zambia's shift to integrated weekday CHTC provision, which they augmented by implementing a change in social norms – another common component of structural interventions. In one Lusaka clinic, Appiagyei and colleagues implemented CHTC, integrated with ANC services. This conference abstract does not provide much detail, but investigators report that “[t]hrough community promotion and fast tracking of clients attending ANC as a couple, this clinic established a social norm for husbands to attend the first antenatal visit with their partner.”

- Over eight months in 2011, 1345 pregnant women received CHTC with their partners.
- Of these, 1117 (64%) were concordant negative, 81 (7%) concordant positive, 80 (6%) discordant, with the male testing HIV-positive, and 59 (4%) discordant with the female testing HIV-positive.

- Investigators do not report this clinic’s baseline CHTC rate nor the number of pregnant women who did not receive CHTC with partners.
- Investigators do not report on adverse events or linkage to care.

Zambia’s 2006 HTC guidance describes three models of service delivery (stand-alone, integrated and mobile/outreach). For each model, the document suggests its possible benefits and constraints. Zambia’s 2006 HTC guidance advises providers that in ANC settings they should follow the country’s PMTCT guidance, without going into further detail. The country’s 2010 PMTCT guidance recommends CHTC in ANC settings, though it is silent on CHTC in other settings. The 2013 integrated HIV guidance speaks only of partner HTC in ANC settings, though it recommends CHTC in other settings. The country’s 2014 HTC implementation plan suggests that CHTC or partner HTC should be encouraged in ANCs. Zambia’s 2006 HTC guidance and its 2014 HTC implementation plan both encourage community promotion and outreach as a means of encouraging individuals and couples to receive CHTC.

7. Methodologic innovation in CHTC disclosure

One study from Kenya described the impact of standardizing methods for counselor-supported disclosure in CHTC.

In four Kenyan counties, Kababu and colleagues (2015) used a quasi-RCT design to test a standardized model for provision of counselor-supported disclosure (CSD) in the CHTC context. Specific components of the model are not described in this conference abstract, but “[t]he model empowered the index clients to invite their sexual partner for CHTC and mutual disclosure.” The model also includes community health worker follow-up with non-responding partners at six weeks and at subsequent points. The study recruited 276 participants for a) standard HTC or CHTC with CSD; or for b) standard HTC or standard CHTC; in the intervention and comparison arms respectively.

- At three months, a larger proportion of participants in the intervention arm than in the comparison arm opted for CHTC (46% vs. 12%).
- Investigators do not report many details, and the difference between groups may not have achieved statistical significance (“the figures were too low for statistical comparison”).

Kenya’s 2015 HTC guidelines provide extensive recommendations for supported disclosure in couples as well as other populations. It is unclear from this conference abstract quite how CSD is

different from other methods for supported disclosure, but the notion of standardizing such methods does seem to be a useful one.

8. Capacity-building

Three reports from the RZHRG describe that organization's recent efforts to help build capacity locally and in other African countries for CHTC provision.

Ahmed and colleagues (2015) report conducting 61 training and technical assistance events in CHTC methods. Between 2009 and 2014, the RZHRG provided workshops, trainings and consultations in 19 African countries. Not all countries were named in this conference abstract, but those named include Botswana, Côte d'Ivoire, Kenya, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda and Swaziland. Technical assistance included high-level advocacy (e.g. engagement with policy-makers, workshops, study tours of RZHRG sites), help with a range of program implementation issues, training of trainers, providers and community health workers; and other technical assistance. Investigators do not report quantitative results but say many countries now have new tools and skills that help them to plan and implement CHTC efforts.

- They report that Botswana and Uganda have rolled out national CHTC strategies and have had good success in implementing CHTC.
- Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana have made "strong commitments" to expanding CHTC and are making good progress toward that end.
- Namibia and South Africa now have many CHTC trainers available to conduct trainings.
- They report that "Kenya, Mozambique, Tanzania and Swaziland have sent high-level observers to Rwanda and Zambia."

In related work, Kilembe and colleagues (2015) report on RZHRG-provided training and technical assistance in Durban, South Africa in 2013. Over the course of five days, five hospital-based clinics received didactic and practical training for local clinic counselors and training on data quality control and cleaning. Local community health volunteers also received didactic and practical training. Clinics then piloted CHTC services. Couples arrived with invitations from promoters or were brought to clinics by trained recruiters. If more than one couple attended simultaneously, pre-test counseling was delivered in group format; couples otherwise began pre-test counseling as a couple. Couples received CHTC, were given results and then counseled together. RZHRG personnel supported all aspects of the pilot implementation.

- Twenty staff counselors and 28 promoters received training.
- Over 12 weekends, clinics provided CHTC to 907 couples.
- HIV prevalence in this population was 41.8%. HIV serodiscordance was 29.5% (male HIV-negative, female HIV-positive: 19.3%; male HIV-positive, female HIV-negative: 10.3%).
- Half (50%) of men and nearly two-thirds (63%) of women reported no prior HTC.
- Investigators report that CHTC was acceptable and feasible to implement in this setting.
- Investigators do not report on linkage to care or adverse events.

Tichacek and colleagues (2014) describe RZHRG's capacity-building efforts for CHTC in Zambia's Copperbelt Province. No CHTC services previously existed in that region. In 2010-2012, investigators engaged in advocacy, conducted needs assessments, and provided training in promotion, counseling, rapid test methods and data reporting methods. In existing clinics and in new CHTC clinics, couples participated in group pre-test sessions, followed by private CHTC with counselor-supported mutual disclosure.

- After 32 months, RZHRG had conducted 314 trainings and opened 53 new CHTC clinics.
- They provided CHTC to 68,347 couples, of whom 6531 (9.6%) were HIV-discordant.
- Around a quarter of individual participants (23.7%) had never previously received HTC.
- Investigators report that their rapid expansion was made possible with support at provincial and national levels, promotions at district and community levels, a multidisciplinary team and monitoring and evaluation.
- Investigators do not report on linkage to care or adverse events.

RZHRG's capacity-building efforts for CHTC in the region seem to go beyond official recommendations of country guidelines. Although Ahmed (2015) reports that Botswana and Uganda have released national CHTC strategies, it is unclear whether they are referring to the 2009 and 2010 HTC guidelines of these countries respectively, or to newer strategic planning documents. Current HTC guidelines of both countries encourage CHTC but emphasis is not strong and there are ambiguities in the guidance. More recent (2012 and 2013 respectively) integrated HIV prevention and treatment guidelines from the two countries are actually deficient in their CHTC guidance. It is possible that the RZHRG team has seen other CHTC policy and planning documents from the two countries.

Similarly, HTC guidelines from Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana (2002 and 2008 respectively) encourage CHTC but do not explicitly recommend it in ANC settings. Ghana's 2014 PMTCT guidelines recommend partner HTC in ANC settings but Côte d'Ivoire's PMTCT and treatment guidelines (2012 and 2013 respectively) are silent on CHTC and partner HTC.

Namibia (2011) and South Africa (2010) both encourage CHTC, but only Namibia recommends CHTC in ANC settings. Subsequent (2014 and 2015 respectively) HIV care and treatment guidance from the two countries does not refer to HTC.

Ahmed and colleagues do not refer in their abstract to ANC-based CHTC, and HTC guidelines for each of these countries antedate WHO's 2012 CHTC guidance. If RZHRG's capacity-building activities for CHTC implementation are aligned with WHO's guidance, it seems possible that the RZHRG team may have seen strategic planning documents and other communiqués from the several countries, not considered in the current review.

South Africa's 2010 HTC guidelines do not describe the use of recruiters to engage couples for CHTC, as reported in Kilembe (2015). Scenarios for CHTC uptake in South Africa's guidance include only client-initiated HTC. Couples are described as a target audience for communication and mobilization efforts. In other respects the training and technical assistance described by Kilembe (2015) aligns well with South Africa's HTC guidelines.

In Zambia, the CHTC process described in a conference abstract by Tichacek (2014) is generally consistent with that country's 2006 HTC recommendations. In addition to integrating CHTC services in existing clinics, it also appears from this conference abstract that they established new stand-alone CHTC clinics.

9. USA government-funded program reports about strategies for CHTC recruitment and implementation

Recent United States (US) Agency for International Development (USAID)-funded program reports provide data suggesting dramatic increases in male ANC attendance and CHTC through implantation of a multi-faceted community-based strategy. The study to which these excerpts refer has apparently not yet (July 2016) been published, though this could change at any time.

- BURUNDI: A figure in the USAID Burundi 2015 report suggest that male partner testing increased from near zero to over 80% within two years. In a subsequent USAID report (USAID ASSIST 2016), another figure from a different district in Burundi suggests an increase

in male partner testing from under 30% to as much as 100%. The reports suggest that the increase was due to the following activities:

- “1) Announcements made in churches and other venues on advantages of accompanying women in ANC visit and HIV testing for couples; 2) Health education session once a week on the advantages of HIV testing for couples; 3) Mobilization of men on PMTCT (importance of accompanying pregnant women in ANC visit and HIV testing for couples) by CHW and community leaders in each sub-colline; 4) Invitation letters for partners.” USAID ASSIST Report 2016

The USAID program reports provide brief accounts of other strategies being implemented in Mozambique, Tanzania and Uganda.

- MOZAMBIQUE: “The team identified that the non-participation of male partners affected early testing, enrollment, and retention of pregnant mothers in the PMTCT program, and identified mothers-in-law as key decision-makers within families and involved them in activities to improve retention of mother-baby pairs. ASSIST Mozambique also sensitized religious leaders to the importance of ANC and asked the religious leaders to share the message with their congregation, which also led to an increase in ANC visits.” – USAID ASSIST 2015
- TANZANIA: “The changes being tested in Arusha include giving PITC to all admissions through allocation of one staff to conduct the PITC, community sensitization meetings to enhance early bookings and male involvement in care, male partners’ invitations, promotion of mother-to-mother groups, screening out admissions to check out for all under 15 and promote PITC to this group, and printing monthly lists of clients who are lost to follow-up.” – USAID ASSIST 2015
- TANZANIA: “During the reporting period there was an increase in male partner testing in both sites compared with aggregate data for the region. This could have been attributed to the following changes tested at Ngerengere and Mafiga sites: offering free blood pressure and weight check for men escorting their partners to RCH; prioritizing couples at RCH; supporting teams on proper and timely ordering of supplies; and involving community leaders to advocate for male involvement.” – USAID Tanzania 2015
- TANZANIA: “USAID ASSIST supported the 14 collaborative sites to integrate PMTCT and RCH in the Kilimanjaro region. Learning sessions were held in 12 out of 13 hospitals in

Kilimanjaro implementing PMTCT QI activities. A total of 65 participants attended the training, including doctors, nursing officers, laboratory technicians, pharmacists, nurse midwives and enrolled nurses from RCH, CTC and labor wards. Coaching and mentoring visits were held with 14 QI sites and 79 QI team members. Substantial improvement was achieved [...] Furthermore, the percentage of pregnant women who were accompanied by their male partners to participate in RCH services increased from 16% in September 2011 to 64% by August 2013.” -- USAID Tanzania 2014

- TANZANIA: “Morogoro region: ASSIST has been following up integration of essential services including inclusion of gender priorities including provision of FP services at the CTC in Morongo... The percentage of male partners tested at RCH every month increased from 17% in January 2012 to 75% in September 2013.” -- USAID Tanzania 2014
- UGANDA: “Although couple counseling and testing is a major challenge, the project continues to provide HCT services to couples using targeted community outreaches. Community dialogue meetings and family health days have provided additional avenues for meeting and testing couples.” – REACH-U 2014
- UGANDA: “During the reporting period, we continued to integrate further demand creation activities with HCT services through health education talks, drama performances, airing of prerecorded voices of influential community members, community dialogue meetings, and IEC materials distribution. These activities mainly targeted couples and MARPs [“most at risk populations”] with information on availability of HCT services, barriers to testing and benefits of knowing ones HIV status among others. [...] Other demand creation activities implemented during the quarter included the health features on HCT access aired on NTV and Bukedde TV stations and talks (Buzz bus) in buses that ply long routes. In Karamoja, a total of 90 influential religious and community leaders participated in meetings and community sensitization activities. This has led to improved attitudes towards HIV/AIDs services, increased awareness and uptake of HCT, other prevention, care and support services in the region.” – REACH-U 2014
- UGANDA: “STAR-EC uses knowledge rooms to deliver health services to key populations.... Many fisher folk spend their leisure time at these venues before their next night duty in the waters. At the knowledge room, different services are provided including recreation (board games, pool table) health educations, condom education and distribution, HTC, couple HTC,

TB screening, referrals and linkages for other biomedical services. More men are attracted to the knowledge room because of the recreational facilities and at the knowledge room they are counseled and linked to access other services.” – STAR-EC 2013

- UGANDA: “Married and/or cohabiting partners were reached through integrated CHTC activities; during community based psychosocial couple support groups meetings and in their homes. Model couples and VHTs [“village health teams”] as linkage facilitators conducted risk reduction counseling among couples focusing on issues of multiple partner reduction; fidelity using ‘families that proposer’, manual aiming to build positive couple communication and planning together for their family; condom promotion and distribution. Structural prevention was promoted using Men & HIV model to discuss issues that make women and girls more vulnerable to HIV infection such as gender based violence, forced marriages, male dominance and permissiveness by women. Efforts were made to link couples and youth to biomedical services including HTC, VMMC [“voluntary male medical circumcision”], family planning and ART for HIV positive individuals [.]” – STAR-EC 2013

Summary analysis and remarks about innovative approaches

We have described the findings of 20 studies of CHTC program delivery, implementation or capacity-building in nine of 21 Global Plan countries, plus Rwanda. Despite comprehensive searches in several major bibliographic databases, with no language restrictions, we found no relevant recent peer-reviewed studies, or even relevant studies reported in recent conference abstracts, from Angola, Botswana, Burundi, Chad, Côte d’Ivoire, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Ghana, Lesotho, Nigeria, Swaziland and Zimbabwe. In part, this may be due to the relatively short horizon of our search frame (2010-2015). It is also possible that in some countries, e.g. Chad, little CHTC programming and implementation work is being done. Or, at least, little is being published about it in peer-reviewed literature or presented in conferences. Targeted searches for specific country research in bibliographic databases were not fruitful. As we show above, we did find some interesting “grey literature” data on the internet for male partner recruitment strategies in Burundi and Tanzania, as well as other notes concerning Mozambique and Uganda.

Within each broad category of studies in the literature arising from peer-reviewed journals and conference abstracts we have briefly considered the degree to which reported activities align with HTC-specific or other HIV guidance from countries in which respective studies were conducted. No study failed to follow core provisions of the respective country’s guidance on HTC. Many studies

conform closely to national HTC policies, while several studies certainly appear to take a step toward global HTC guidance – a step beyond the national recommendations.

For example, Becker (2014) in Malawi conducted home-based CHTC despite that country's HTC guidance omitting to mention couples as appropriate targets of such community-based interventions. Similarly, Brunie (2016) in offering CHTC with FP counseling go further than Uganda's guidance explicitly recommends. Other examples from Malawi include the work of Nyondo (2015) and Rosenberg (2015). The country's HTC guidance is silent about the need to engage male partners in women's pregnancy and HTC, but investigators in both studies made efforts to do just that with invitations. The situation in Mozambique's HTC guidance is similar, but Audet (2016) increased male partner HTC through their "male champions" intervention. South Africa's 2010 HTC guidance or 2015 integrated HIV guidance do not describe the use of recruiters to find couples for CHTC, but this strategy was used by Kilembe (2015) in their pilot CHTC implementation.

Kenyan HTC guidance does not state that CHTC could be offered in home-based HTC efforts, but Osofi (2014), Mark (2015) and Krakowiak (2016) all worked to increase CHTC in home visits. Mozambique too is not explicit about CHTC in this context, but Bandomia (2013) implemented CHTC in home-based HTC. Zambia's "structural" move in 2011 to integrate CHTC into the weekday practice of government clinics, as described by Appiagyei (2012) and Inambao (2014) was also not anticipated by its 2006 HTC guidance or its 2010 PMTCT guidance, nor is it reflected in the country's 2013 general HIV guidance. It does appear in the country's 2014 HTC planning document. Details are sparse in the study by Appiagyei (2012) in which investigators apparently changed social norms around male engagement in PMTCT care, but this also is not a facet of any guidance from Zambia.

Countries lacking data for innovative approaches

Without the contributions of studies reporting results of innovative approaches to CHTC programming in countries not represented in this paper, we are unable to consider and provide analysis about the unique situations that obtain in these settings and any innovative work that is being done. For several countries, however, we have qualitative and other data about implementation challenges and barriers to service uptake. We describe these in the next section of the paper.

Challenges to policy adoption, program implementation and service uptake

Barriers to CHTC uptake and challenges to CHTC implementation can occur on several levels. At the level of national policy, problems may include ambiguity or a lack of clarity in language, non-alignment with global HTC guidance (reflected in promotion of obsolete standards or in simply not being up-to-date) and conflicting guidance. National guideline developers may have different understandings about the meanings of technical terms used in global HTC guidance. In developing guidelines, countries may consult older iterations of global HTC guidance. They may provide only summary HTC guidance in the context of more general country guidelines for HIV prevention and care.

At the level of health systems, implementers and healthcare providers may misinterpret national HTC guidance, may rely on obsolete or summary versions or may not have access to it at all. If national HTC guidance itself is old or obsolete in comparison to global guidance, they may need to work within those constraints, though as we have seen, implementers sometimes also move beyond them. They may lack appropriate training. Sociocultural and infrastructural considerations may also inform implementation and clinical practice. Sex roles and cultural concerns also factor strongly into couples' (and individual men's and women's) decision-making about HTC acceptance and serostatus disclosure.

For each of these levels, we describe here some of the barriers and challenges that we perceived in national policy documents, in peer-reviewed literature and in other programmatic reports. Please see Table 6.

Table 6. Summary of CHTC uptake & implementation challenges and barriers

National policy	Implementation & practice	Couples and individuals
Ambiguous or unclear language	Providers disclose to partners without consent	Socioeconomic barriers, distances, costs
Conflicting guidance among several country guidance documents	Long wait times, crowded clinics, inadequate staffing & supplies	Health systems barriers, not a male-friendly environment, perceived rudeness of providers
Idiosyncrasies of national guideline development processes	Compulsory HIV testing as condition of ANC attendance	Stigma arising from cultural beliefs/gender roles
Inconsistency in source of global guidance	Compulsory male partner HTC as a condition of ANC attendance	Cultural beliefs/gender roles preclude man listening to woman or doing what she asks
Lack of national HTC guidance	Clinic & provider failure to request male partner HTC or CHTC	Lack of knowledge/wrong ideas
Old documents and policies obsolete by global standards	HIV testing with no counseling	Existing marriage problems, suspicion
Referral to other documents for answer to relevant question	Compulsory use of de-worming tablets	Fear of testing HIV-positive
Supersession by larger HIV guidance that provides inadequate detail	Providers poorly trained in HTC	Fear of violence or marriage problems if testing HIV-positive

1. National policy

Earlier in this review, we described the specific ways in which national HTC policies of the 22 countries align or do not align with WHO's 2012 CHTC guidance. In this section we will examine larger issues in regard to country HTC policies that could potentially lead to difficulties in implementation or practice. Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4 will again be of interest.

Our general sense of the landscape of national HTC policy and guidance in the 22 countries is that it is inconsistent and idiosyncratic. Country HTC recommendations are articulated in very new, dedicated, HTC-specific publications as well as in 10-15 year old documents that are likely perceived by stakeholders as ancient. In countries without HTC-specific guidelines, HTC and especially CHTC guidance may only be expressed briefly in a paragraph or two.

Several countries (Angola, Burundi, Cameroon, Chad, Lesotho and Rwanda) have not released HTC-specific guidelines. (In our review, we used Chad's national HTC training manual in an attempt to discern country CHTC policies.)

- Without specific and detailed HTC guidelines, program implementers and clinicians could have difficulty in applying country policy.

In many countries (Botswana, Côte d'Ivoire, Ethiopia, Ghana, Namibia, Nigeria, South Africa, Uganda, Zambia), HTC-specific guidelines antedate WHO's 2012 CHTC guidance. Similarly, more recent HTC-specific guidelines (Kenya, Malawi, Mozambique, Tanzania) refer to other iterations of WHO's HTC guidance, ranging from WHO's 2007 guidance on provider-initiated testing and counseling (Tanzania) to WHO's 2012 guidance on HTC service delivery approaches (Kenya, Malawi) to WHO's 2015 consolidated guidance on HIV testing services (Mozambique).

- Even where national HTC policy documents align well with current WHO guidance, there are bound to be minor inconsistencies and nuances of terminology and emphasis where policies diverge.
- In the context of the more recent guidelines, the concern is not that countries following parallel WHO guidance for HTC would necessarily fall into "error." It is that each of the WHO documents followed has its own respective areas of emphasis, and national guideline developers may follow some areas and not others. For example, proponents of CHTC in ANCs may be disappointed in Mozambique (2015) and Tanzania (2013) recommending only

partner testing in ANCs. This is by no means a bad thing, but it is not the same as CHTC. Similarly, Kenya (2015) recommends CHTC in maternal and child health care settings, and does not specify ANCs. This is not technically incorrect, but it does somewhat have the effect of de-emphasizing the specific need for CHTC where pregnant women attend ANCs with their male partners.

Although countries may have HTC-specific guidelines, nearly all will also have other guidance for ART or PMTCT, or they may publish more broadly-framed “integrated” or “consolidated” guidance covering HIV prevention, treatment and treatment-as-prevention. This is of course necessary, but HTC-specific recommendations may be treated much more summarily in these documents than was done in the documents dedicated to HTC. Similarly, countries without HTC-specific documents may provide very little or even no guidance in regard to CHTC.

- In available and current national guidance, only Cameroon (2014), Ethiopia (2014), Rwanda (2013), Swaziland (2015) and Zambia (2010 – PMTCT guidance) followed all three of WHO’s major 2012 CHTC recommendations. Botswana (2012), Cote d'Ivoire (2012, 2013), Democratic Republic of Congo (2013), Kenya (2013), Namibia (2014), Nigeria (2014), South Africa (2015), Uganda (2012) and Zimbabwe (2014) follow none, though this may be beyond the remit of some guidance focused primarily on treatment.

With regard to HTC and CHTC in ANC settings, HTC-specific guidance from Ethiopia (2007) and Zambia (2006) refer interested readers to other documents providing PMTCT guidance for the respective countries. Current PMTCT guidance is much newer (2013 and 2010 respectively) and does indeed recommend offering CHTC in ANC settings. It is unclear whether earlier PMTCT guidance was similarly aligned to WHO’s 2012 CHTC guidance. Another problem with this tactic, however, is that the reader is referred to a document that may be inaccessible. Simply providing guidance in the very document at hand would be better, especially since it purports to provide HTC recommendations.

In countries with HTC-specific documents, especially older documents, the extent to which program implementers and healthcare providers have access to them is unclear. It is also unclear whether HTC-specific documents are still used when they are apparently superseded by (or are deemed less convenient than) more comprehensive HIV guidelines. For example, it is unclear whether Uganda’s 2010 HTC guideline is still followed when the country’s current “integrated” document’s

introductory section declares that “[t]his 2012 booklet combines the updated national guidelines into one easy to use tool for health providers.” Yet as we have seen, Uganda’s 2012 document is inadequate in its consideration of HTC and CHTC.

- If HTC and especially CHTC recommendations were given adequate and WHO-consistent consideration in the larger “integrated” national policy documents, it is possible that existing HTC documents could indeed be superseded. In the current context, however, even where larger national guideline documents align with WHO’s 2012 recommendations, it is not clear that there the larger documents provide sufficient nuance and detail for appropriate implementation.

Beyond country HTC and other HIV guidelines, the program reports and other documents developed by local NGO partners and Ministry of Health staff for international funding agencies may give mixed messages about the value of CHTC.

- An end-of-project report by the United States Agency for International Development (USAID)-funded “Realizing Expanded Access to Counseling and Testing for HIV in Uganda (REACH-U) program reports implementation statistics, success stories, challenges and other data (REACH-U 2014). The document notes in several places the difficulties involved in recruiting couples. Early in the document, the Ministry of Health’s National HTC Coordinator urges continued effort on CHTC, despite these difficulties. Later in the document, another writer (not attributed) provides a conflicting view: “Testing people in a sexual relation as couples is becoming increasingly less feasible in many cultural contexts because a majority of people in Uganda do not ‘conduct business’ as couples but rather as individuals. We recommend individual HCT, since efficiencies can be attained when people are tested more as individuals than couples.”

2. Challenges in implementation and for health systems

In considering challenges to CHTC program implementation and practice, the general difficulties of infrastructure, stock-outs and other elements in many areas of sub-Saharan Africa are well known. In this section we will look at issues of specific relevance to HTC, whether these are reported by patients or health system personnel.

Adekanle and colleagues (2015) in Osogbo, Nigeria interviewed 122 married women living with HIV in an effort to understand the parameters of HIV status disclosure when they received HTC.

- Only 28 (23%) male partners knew the women's serostatus.
- Of these, counselors had disclosed the serostatus of 25 (89.3%) women to male partners and family members without the women's consent.
- These women subsequently experienced sexual deprivation and stigma.
- Only 29 (23.8%) women were aware that their male partner had also received HTC.
- Of these, four (3.3%) male partners were known to have been diagnosed HIV-positive.
- This report does not address CHTC or male partner HTC.

Ahumuza and colleagues (2016) in Katakwi and Mubende districts, Uganda, used focus group discussions to collect data from 89 pregnant or postpartum women attending ANCs and key informant interviews with 21 district managers and health workers in an effort to understand challenges faced in providing integrated HIV, antenatal and postnatal care services.

- Overall, challenges were contextualized in terms of insufficient staffing and staff absenteeism, knowledge gaps in service providers, shortage of critical supplies and inadequate clinic space.
- More specifically, challenges included the following: Long wait times; omission of vital measurements and laboratory tests; limited provider skills in all aspects of HTC; coercive or compulsory use of de-worming tablets; large breaches of HIV-status confidentiality and lack of private spaces; expectant mothers waiting in small rooms with tuberculosis patients; too much paperwork; and negative attitude of health workers toward additional work.
- CHTC or male partner testing are not mentioned in this report.

Asiyanbola and colleagues (2016) in Ibadan, Nigeria conducted focus group discussions with 40 pregnant women accessing antenatal care at three government hospitals. Using checklists, investigators also made observations and took inventories. Date or timeframe of the study were not reported. Data collected highlighted serious deficiencies in hospital HTC practice. Among the deficiencies reported were the following:

- Women received no pre-test counseling and were not given the opportunity to receive HTC voluntarily; testing was mandatory if they wished to receive ANC services.
- Hospital staff handed test results directly to women without the benefit of post-test counseling.
- No testing of male partners was done.

Investigators suggest also that hospital staff were poorly trained. Hospitals had inadequate supplies and no dedicated counseling room.

Musheke and colleagues (2013) in Lusaka, Zambia report the experiences of 10 couples who had received CHTC, seven individuals who had received CHTC but were subsequently abandoned by spouses, five HTC counselors and two nurses. In-depth interviews were used with CHTC recipients and key informant interviews were used with clinic personnel. Interviews were conducted between March 2010 and September 2011. Key findings are quoted verbatim.

- “Health workers sometimes used coercive and subtle strategies to enlist women’s spouses for couple HIV testing resulting in some men feeling ‘trapped’ or ‘forced’ to test as part of their paternal responsibility. Couple testing had some positive outcomes, notably disclosure of HIV status to marital partner, renewed commitment to marital relationship, uptake of and adherence to treatment and formation of new social networks. However, there were also negative repercussions including abandonment, verbal abuse and cessation of sexual relations. Its promotion also did not always lead to safe sex as this was undermined by gendered power relationships and the desires for procreation and sexual intimacy.”

Påfs and colleagues (2015) in Kigali, Rwanda used a range of qualitative approaches to explore the perspectives of women who had nearly died during pregnancy (“near miss”), and understand paradoxical barriers to care introduced by the health system. Data were collected between March 2013 and April 2014. Key findings are quoted verbatim.

- “All informants were aware of the recommendations of male involvement for HIV-testing at the first antenatal care visit. However, this recommendation was seen as a clear link in the chain of delays and led to severe consequences, especially for women without engaged partners.”
- “The overall quality of antenatal services was experienced as suboptimal, potentially missing the opportunity to provide preventive measures and essential health education intended for both parents. This seemed to contribute to women’s disincentive to complete all four recommended visits and men’s interest in attending to ensure their partners’ reception of care. However, the participants experienced a restriction of men’s access during subsequent antenatal visits, which made men feel denied to their increased involvement during pregnancy.”

Other anecdotal evidence

In a [January 2015 blog post](#) on the web site of the Maternal Health Task Force (Harvard School of Public Health), Dr. S. Kiwanuka of Makerere University responded to Uganda's November 2014 announcement of an initiative to increase male partner involvement in maternal health care. Suggesting that the policy could potentially result in harms to women, Dr. Kiwanuka provides brief narrative quotes from women who have experienced such harms. Dr. Kiwanuka does not attribute these quotes and it is unclear whether they emerged from her own research or came from other sources. We present these quotes verbatim.

- “I went to the facility when my pregnancy was 2 month but was denied access to services because I had not gone with my husband. I again went there when it was 6 months and the same happened. I decided to go back home and wait for the time of delivery because I had nothing to do. My husband is not always at home. I tried to explain to the health worker but she could not listen to me. When the time for delivery reached, I decided to deliver from home because I feared to go back to the facility. Two days after delivery, my child died. – Ugandan Mother”
- “Mmmhmmm!... (with a shrug) ...If a woman comes without a spouse we send them to another facility where services might not be as good as here. – Midwife in Northern Uganda”

Recent news reports provide could some additional evidence of problems in health systems, community understanding and HTC delivery. These reports are simply news articles found on the internet. They may not be accurate.

- The [Bulawayo \(Zimbabwe\) Chronicle reported](#) in June 2016 that husbands in Gokwe village (Midlands Province) who failed to accompany pregnant wives to ANCs and receive HTC would be “fined a goat” by village chiefs.
- A December 2015 [report from Uganda on AllAfrica.com](#) suggests that pregnant women attending ANC at Mukongoro Health Centre were turned away if not accompanied by their husbands. Women hired boda-boda riders to pose as husbands.
- An August 2015 [report in the Lagos \(Nigeria\) Daily Post](#) suggests that some churches may not be performing marriages unless couples first receive HTC.

3. Challenges and barriers for couples and individuals

We identified two recent systematic reviews (Morfaw 2013, Manjate Cuco 2015) that provide abundant detail about couple and male partner barriers to HTC uptake. As there was very substantial overlap between the reviews in terms of studies found, and rigor of review methods was about equal, we present key findings of the more recent review.

Manjate Cuco and colleagues (2015) conducted a systematic review of male involvement in PMTCT efforts in sub-Saharan Africa. Reviewers searched PubMed and Google Scholar in December 2013 for publications in the English language. They also searched “grey literature,” as well as documents from WHO and other agencies, but these materials were not considered in the current review. Reviewers sought published articles on male involvement in PMTCT, HTC and HIV status disclosure. They identified 11 quantitative and 13 qualitative studies and four with mixed methods. Studies were conducted in Uganda (k=6), Kenya (k=5), Tanzania (k=5), Zambia (k=4), South Africa (k=3), Cameroon (k=2), Malawi (k=2), Côte d’Ivoire (k=1), Democratic Republic of Congo (3%), and Rwanda (k=1). All studies were observational in design. Twenty-four of 28 studies identified reported on barriers to male engagement. Barriers included the following:

- Socioeconomic barriers (11 studies)
 - Distance to clinics and financial burdens in reaching them, especially for a couple
 - Work commitments
 - Time constraints
- Health systems barriers (11 studies)
 - Feeling ignored and “left out” in PMTCT clinics
 - Feeling uncomfortable in crowded PMTCT clinics
 - Discomfort with rude or harsh attitude of health workers, including toward female partners
- Cultural beliefs and gender roles (17 studies)
 - Concerns that accompaniment to a “female gathering” implied yielding power to women
 - Concerns that female partner HTC implied adultery or prostitution

- Concerns about community criticism, “weakness,” loss of masculinity, “bewitchment”
- Fear of community hostility, “setting a bad example” for other couples
- Fear of being the only male at the clinic
- Lack of knowledge (14 studies)
 - Belief that men’s HIV status would always be the same as female partner HIV status
 - Belief that PMTCT is only women’s responsibility
 - Unclear on why men should receive HTC
 - Unclear on role of HTC when no symptoms are evident
 - Unclear on role of ANCs and PMTCT if mother and baby are well
- Other male fears (11 studies)
 - Fear of unwanted HIV disclosure
 - Fear of marital disharmony
- Existing problems in the marriage (nine studies)
 - Characterize marriage as unstable or distrustful
 - Suspicions of extramarital affairs
 - Cultural standards concerning female-initiated conversations and of men ignoring information provided by women
 - Belief that female partners are withholding or distorting information from them

Several studies published subsequent to the searches conducted for Manjate Cuco’s review provide additional perspective on barriers to CHTC and partner HTC uptake in both men and women.

Matovu and colleagues (2014) in Rakai, Uganda used focus group discussions, in-depth interviews and key informant interviews to explore barriers to and motivations for CHTC uptake. From August to October 2013, investigators conducted 18 focus group discussions that included 142 married individuals, 71 (50%) males and 71 females. Fifty individuals (35.2%) had previously received CHTC; 47 (33.1%) had received individual HTC; 45 (31.7%) had never received HTC. Investigators conducted six in-depth interviews with previous CHTC recipients and nine key informant interviews with HIV counselors (n=3), community health mobilizers (n=3) and religious leaders (n=3).

Investigators do not stratify responses by sex. Barriers to CHTC uptake were generally consistent with those identified in the systematic review by Manjate Cuco (2015). The primary barriers were as follows (quoted verbatim).

- Fear of receiving concordant HIV-positive or HIV-discordant results
- Fear of marital violence or dissolution
- Fear that couples' HCT could expose hidden infidelity
- Fear of being ashamed before one's partner in the event of an HIV-positive status
- Urge by one or both partners to hide HIV status from each other
- Lack of trust/misunderstandings in the home
- Men's reluctance/refusal to test for HIV together with their partners
- Conflicting schedules between men and women

Investigators also report the following factors that helped to enable CHTC uptake (quoted verbatim).

- Hold couple-specific meetings to sensitize couples on the benefits of couples' HIV testing
- Send invitation letters to couples
- Promote couples' HCT by going to people's homes
- Use religious leaders to sensitize their flock about couples' HCT
- Provide preferential treatment to couples when they come to test for HIV together
- Use expert couples, i.e., couples that have ever tested together to motivate others to test for HIV together

In Zambézia, Mozambique, where they were conducting the "male champions" intervention described above, Audet and colleagues (2015) conducted 14 community focus group discussions in an effort to understand ANC service uptake, including HTC. Focus groups included 122 participants, of whom 99 (81.1%) were community members and 23 (18.9%) were clinical staff. Breakdown by sex was not reported. The main barriers were based on traditional gender roles and community beliefs.

- Socially unacceptable for men to visibly support partners
- Women are responsible for their pregnancies
- Avoidance of HIV testing (i.e. because it is common knowledge that women receive HTC at first ANC visit)
- Social stigma – ANC attendance implies HIV-positive status

Investigators note that in contrast to other research in sub-Saharan Africa, perceived poor treatment by physicians did not emerge as a major barrier to male engagement.

CONCLUSIONS and RECOMMENDATIONS

In this wide-ranging review, we have attempted to analyze national HTC policies of the 21 EMTCT Global Plan priority countries in sub-Saharan Africa, plus Rwanda, both in the context of WHO's 2012 CHTCT guidance and in that of innovative, recently emerging HTC research.

As we have seen, country HTC guidelines published subsequent to WHO's 2012 CHTC recommendations align with WHO fairly well. It is a much more mixed scenario in regard to national HTC guidance published before 2012, as well as with other current and available country HIV guidelines. Alignment with WHO policy is quite inconsistent and recommendations are sometimes unclear. In examining new studies aiming to increase or optimize CHTC uptake and implementation we found that in no case did investigators fail to follow country recommendations. In several studies, however, investigators seemed to expand the contexts of specific policy areas (e.g. offering CHTC in ANCs when only "partner HTC" is specifically recommended; or making efforts to engage male partners when country guidance is silent in the topic). In such cases, ongoing research in a given country may be aligned more closely with WHO policy and international standards than national guidance meant to underpin that research. And indeed, some strategies we have reviewed in this paper seem to have benefited from such innovation. They may hold promise for replication in other settings; perhaps tested as part of multifaceted suite of approaches in which the whole is greater than the sum of its inexpensive and easily implemented parts.

While academic researchers and health ministry personnel may be well aware of the parameters of country health guidance, and can potentially enhance health and care organization outcomes through nuanced adjustments to interventions, this may not be the case at all for health workers and clinicians. Even when health care facilities have adequate supplies and staffing, providers and community health workers may struggle to understand "which guideline" they should follow in implementing HTC and CHTC appropriately. Guideline language may be ambiguous. Despite best efforts, there are many wrong paths down which one could go.

Beyond the potential for this type of confusion, however, patients and providers alike may face difficulties and even near chaos in the routine course of a clinic's day. These problems far exceed the scope of HTC and even of HIV. They are often quite complex and multidimensional, and simply having clear, straightforward and up-to-date CHTC and partner HTC guidance will not solve everything.

However, there are likely some ways to keep country HTC guidance internally consistent while at the same time harmonizing it with WHO guidance and that of other African countries.

We have considered only 22 of the 47 countries included in WHO's African Regional Office (AFRO). The other 25 countries are no less diverse in their cultures, histories, socioeconomic and political contexts and of course their experiences and response to more than 30 years of HIV/AIDS. If we may step a bit higher for perspective, we wish to make a recommendation about potential ways to improve national HTC guidance in AFRO. Following this, we will make additional recommendations relevant to other aspects of this report.

The World Health Assembly approved WHO's Global Health Sector Strategy on HIV/AIDS in May 2016. In August 2016, just one month from this writing, health ministers from the 47 AFRO countries will meet in Addis Ababa for the sixty-sixth meeting of WHO's Regional Committee for Africa. Members will discuss WHO's HIV/AIDS Framework for Action, 2016-2020, within which a prominent high-priority "intervention for impact" is this one:

- *Expand national HIV testing services. It is important to diversify testing approaches and services by combining provider-initiated and community-based testing, promoting decentralization of services and utilizing HIV testing services to detect other infections and health conditions. HIV testing services need to be focused on reaching populations and settings where the HIV/AIDS burden is greatest in order to achieve greater impact. All countries should ensure that HIV testing services meet ethical and quality standards.*¹

Members will also be encouraged to review and update their respective national HIV/AIDS strategies and guidelines.

WHO might consider taking these excellent recommendations a step further. Given the variable interpretations and forms of WHO's HTC guidance in existing national policies and guidelines, it may be worth taking some effort to harmonize future ones. Should countries publish their main national HTC and CHTC guidance in dedicated, stand-alone documents? Should such guidance mainly appear in the country's PMTCT guidance, or perhaps its integrated antiretroviral guidance? How frequently should it be updated? If a stand-alone document, how to ensure both that larger integrated

¹ World Health Organization, Regional Committee for Africa. Sixty-sixth session, Addis Ababa, Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia, 19-23 August 2016. Provisional agenda item 13.

guidelines would mirror it, and that it would still be used by stakeholders? Which WHO guideline should countries follow in developing their HTC policies? Much is currently open to interpretation. As a first recommendation, we suggest that WHO consider the possibility of convening a regional meeting (or perhaps parallel regional meetings, given the several languages) of Ministry personnel engaged in each country's HIV guideline development. The specific focus would be to agree upon standards for optimal application of WHO's HTC recommendations in national guidelines, and to be clear about precisely what these recommendations are. It is not possible, of course, to impose a "cookie-cutter" approach, nor would this even be desirable, but if key messages (including nuances of terminology) can be understood, and within any country feasibility or cost constraints, agreed upon for use, they may translate well to the eventual national documents. If WHO has not already done so, it might also be worth exploring the possibility of developing a succinct but thorough guide to "implementing" its HTC and CHTC recommendations – as national guidelines.

Our second recommendation pertains to interventions for improving CHTC and partner HTC uptake and implementation. It is much in keeping with the passage above from the AFRO meeting agenda. We agree that a diverse range of integrative and decentralized approaches is needed in order to achieve maximum impact and suggest that program implementers be encouraged to "think outside the box" in terms of developing multifaceted strategies. We have examined several such approaches in this report, and believe that with appropriate monitoring and evaluation and the possibility of recalibrating if needed, this type of strategy can be customized well to local settings.

Our final recommendation concerns structural interventions, which as we mentioned previously, aim to improve accessibility, acceptability and availability of services (Blankenship 2006). They often also include components of change in social norms (Blankenship 2006). The conference abstract by Appiagyei (2012) described above tells precious little about how they were able to change social norms. Even if this turns out to be somewhat overstated, however, structural approaches may be the most appropriate for resolving male barriers to engagement in maternal care. We recommend that program implementers and national, provincial or district policy makers begin or continue dialogue aimed at developing such structural interventions.

DECLARATIONS of INTEREST

We have no financial or other conflicts of interest to disclose.

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Electronic files for each included study may be downloaded here: <https://goo.gl/GrNxms>

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Country HIV guidance and policy documents

All country guidance and policy documents may be found here: <https://goo.gl/GrNxmS>

HTC-specific	
Country and publication year	Title
Botswana 2009	NATIONAL GUIDELINES: HIV TESTING AND COUNSELLING
Chad 2011	MANUEL DE FORMATION EN COUNSELING VIH/SIDA/IST
Côte d'Ivoire 2002	DOCUMENT DE NORMES ET DIRECTIVES NATIONALES DU CONSEIL ET DEPISTAGE VOLONTAIRE DU VIH EN COTE D'IVOIRE
DR Congo 2004	NORMES ET DIRECTIVES EN CONSEIL ET DEPISTAGE VOLONTAIRE DU VIH/SIDA
Ethiopia 2007	Guidelines for HIV Counselling and Testing in Ethiopia
Ghana 2008	NATIONAL GUIDELINES FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF HIV COUNSELING AND TESTING IN GHANA
Kenya 2015	THE KENYA HIV TESTING SERVICES GUIDELINES
Malawi 2015	HIV TESTING SERVICES (HTS) GUIDELINES, 4 th edition (DRAFT COPY)

Malawi 2013	MALAWI COMPREHENSIVE HIV TESTING AND COUNSELLING TRAINING: PARTICIPANT HANDBOOK
Mozambique 2015	DIRECTRIZ NACIONAL PARA A IMPLEMENTAÇÃO DO ACONSELHAMENTO E TESTAGEM EM SAÚDE (PROOFING COPY)
Namibia 2011	National Guidelines for HIV Counselling and Testing in Namibia
Nigeria 2011	NATIONAL GUIDELINES FOR HIV COUNSELLING AND TESTING
Swaziland 2006	HIV TESTING AND COUNSELLING NATIONAL GUIDELINES
South Africa 2010	NATIONAL HIV COUNSELLING AND TESTING (HCT) POLICY GUIDELINES
Tanzania 2013	National Comprehensive Guidelines for HIV Testing and Counselling
Uganda 2010	UGANDA HIV COUNSELLING AND TESTING POLICY, 3 rd edition
Zambia 2014	HIV TESTING AND COUNSELLING (HTC) IMPLEMENTATION PLAN (2014-2016)
Zambia 2006	NATIONAL GUIDELINES FOR HIV COUNSELLING & TESTING
Zimbabwe 2014	ZIMBABWE National Guidelines on HIV Testing and Counselling
Not HTC-specific	
Country and publication year	Title
Angola 2014	PROTOCOLO PARA AVALIAÇÃO E SEGUIMENTO DE ENFERMAGEM AOS PACIENTES VIH+
Botswana 2012	Botswana National HIV & AIDS Treatment Guidelines
Burundi 2014	DIRECTIVES NATIONALES DE TRAITEMENT ANTI RETROVIRALE DE L'INFECTION PAR LE VIH AU BURUNDI
Cameroon 2014	DIRECTIVES NATIONALES DE PREVENTION ET DE PRISE EN CHARGE DU VIH AU CAMEROUN
Cameroon 2006	Prévention de la Transmission du VIH de la Mère à l'Enfant: Guide de Poche
Chad 2011	PLAN STRATEGIQUE NATIONAL DE RIPOSTE AU SIDA 2012-2015
Côte d'Ivoire 2013	DIRECTIVES POUR LA PRISE EN CHARGE DES PVVIH
Côte d'Ivoire 2012	DIRECTIVES NATIONALES DE MISE SOUS ANTIRETROVIRAUX DES FEMMES ENCEINTES DEPISTÉES SEROPOSITIVES AU VIH DANS LE CADRE DE LA PREVENTION DE LA TRANSMISSION MERE-ENFANT DU VIH (PTME)
Ethiopia 2014	NATIONAL GUIDELINES FOR COMPREHENSIVE HIV PREVENTION, CARE AND TREATMENT
Ghana 2014	National Guidelines for Prevention of Mother to Child Transmission of HIV
Kenya 2014	Guidelines on Use of Antiretroviral Drugs for Treating and Preventing HIV Infection: Rapid advice

Kenya 2012	GUIDELINES FOR PREVENTION OF MOTHER TO CHILD TRANSMISSION (PMTCT) OF HIV/AIDS IN KENYA, 4 th edition
Lesotho 2014	NATIONAL GUIDELINES ON THE USE OF ANTIRETROVIRAL THERAPY FOR HIV PREVENTION AND TREATMENT
Malawi 2014	Clinical Management of HIV in Children and Adults
Mozambique 2014	Guia de Tratamento Antiretroviral e Infecções Oportunistas no Adulto, Criança, Adolescente e Grávida
Namibia 2014	National Guidelines for Antiretroviral Therapy
Nigeria 2014	National HIV/AIDS Prevention Plan
Rwanda 2013	National Guidelines for Prevention and Management of HIV, STIs & Other Blood Borne Infections
South Africa 2015	NATIONAL CONSOLIDATED GUIDELINES FOR THE PREVENTION OF MOTHER-TO-CHILD TRANSMISSION OF HIV (PMTCT) AND THE MANAGEMENT OF HIV IN CHILDREN, ADOLESCENTS AND ADULTS
Swaziland 2015	Swaziland Integrated HIV Management Guidelines
Tanzania 2014	NATIONAL GUIDELINE FOR COMPREHENSIVE PACKAGE OF HIV INTERVENTIONS FOR KEY POPULATIONS
Tanzania 2013	National Guidelines for Comprehensive Services for Prevention of Mother-to-Child Transmission of HIV and Keeping Mothers Alive (PMTCT)
Uganda 2012	National Guidelines on Antiretroviral Therapy, Prevention of Mother to Child Transmission of HIV, Infant & Young Child Feeding
Uganda 2013	ADDENDUM TO THE NATIONAL ANTIRETROVIRAL TREATMENT GUIDELINES
Zambia 2010	National Protocol Guidelines: Integrated Prevention of Mother-to-Child Prevention of HIV
Zambia 2013	Zambia Consolidated Guidelines for Treatment and Prevention of HIV Infection
Zimbabwe 2013	Guidelines for Antiretroviral Therapy for the Prevention and Treatment of HIV in Zimbabwe

APPENDIX 1: OTHER RELEVANT RESEARCH

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FIGURE 1. Map: Twenty-one Global Plan EMTCT priority countries, plus Rwanda

